

Restoring Form and Function: Cheek Flap Reconstruction of a Nasolabial Defect Following Basal Cell Carcinoma Excision

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: To describe wide local excision and single-stage cheek advancement flap reconstruction for nasolabial basal cell carcinoma (BCC), and evaluate early outcomes including flap viability, complications, and facial nerve function.

Background: Nasolabial BCC reconstruction requires balancing oncologic clearance with preservation of contour and facial dynamics. Cheek advancement flaps offer good tissue match and vascularity.

Methods: A 60-year-old woman with a 2.7 cm × 2.7 cm nasolabial nodular-infiltrative BCC underwent wide excision (defect 4 cm × 3 cm) and immediate cheek flap reconstruction. Outcomes included flap viability, complications, and facial nerve function across three follow-ups.

Results: Flap viability was preserved without necrosis, infection, hematoma, or dehiscence. The patient was discharged on day 6. Facial nerve function was largely intact, with mild transient smile asymmetry. Aesthetic outcomes were favorable.

Conclusions: Cheek advancement flap provides reliable single-stage reconstruction for moderate nasolabial defects. Further studies are needed to assess long-term outcomes.

KEYWORDS: basal cell carcinoma; nasolabial defect; cheek advancement flap; facial reconstruction; flap viability

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I. INTRODUCTION

Basal cell carcinoma (BCC) is the most common form of skin cancer with a strong predilection for sun-exposed areas of the head and neck. Chronic ultraviolet radiation exposure remains the principal etiologic factor, elderly patients with prolonged outdoor activity therefore represent a high-risk population. Although BCC demonstrates low metastatic potential, untreated or delayed lesions may exhibit locally aggressive behavior, leading to significant functional and aesthetic impairment.^{I,II} Facial BCCs located in the nasolabial and perinasal regions present reconstructive challenges because excision must balance oncologic safety (clear margins) with preservation of nasal contour, oral commissure function, and facial expression. In these cases, immediate reconstruction using local flaps is favored to achieve optimal

functional and aesthetic outcomes while minimizing donor-site morbidity.^{III,IV}

In recent reconstructive practice, the cheek advancement flap has gained renewed attention as a practical and reliable option for reconstruction of nasolabial and perinasal defects following oncologic excision, this flap offer excellent color and texture match and permit coverage of moderate-sized nasolabial and lateral nasal defects with generally favorable functional and aesthetic outcomes. Recent comparative series and outcome studies report high flap viability and acceptable complication rates, while ongoing debate remains about superficial-plane versus deep-plane dissection to optimize vascularity and reduce flap morbidity.^{V,VI}

We present a case of nodular-infiltrating BCC of the nasolabial region reconstructed with a cheek advancement

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flap after wide excision. This report illustrates surgical decision-making for oncologic safety and immediate reconstruction in an elderly patient with sun-exposure risk, and contributes practical outcome data to the growing literature on locoregional flap algorithms for facial skin cancer defects.

II. CASE PRESENTATION

A 60-year-old female patient was consulted by a surgical oncologist presented with a facial lesion suspicious for malignancy on the right nasolabial region. The patient complained of a lump on the right side of her face, with near proximity to the right nostril, which had been occurring for the past year. Initially, it was a nevus that had been growing larger over the past year. The complaint was accompanied by itching and pain on the lesion, and occasionally there were intermittent wounds. The patient has used several over-the-counter topical medications but the symptoms did not improve. The patient is a farmer with a history of daily direct sun exposure without the use of sunscreen. Similar lesion on other parts of the body are denied. Patient denied history of surgery, and had no family history with a similar condition. The patient has a history of hypertension and type 2 diabetes mellitus and was being treated with 5mg of amlodipine once a day and 500mg of metformin twice a day.

Fig 1. Physical examination demonstrates a raised lesion, black and brown in color, irregular surface, with indistinct border, measuring approximately 2.7 cm x 2.7 cm on the right nasolabial region.

On physical examination of the right nasolabial region, there was a 2.7 cm x 2.7 cm lesion, black and brown in color, irregular surface, with indistinct border. No wounds, pus, or exudate were noted. Preoperative evaluation revealed no abnormalities in cardiac or pulmonary assessment and no evidence of metastatic involvement in the lungs or bones. Laboratory investigations were within normal limits, indicating stable hematologic, hepatic, and renal function.

Preoperatively, the patient received prophylactic antibiotic coverage with a single intravenous dose of ceftriaxone 2 grams. The patient then underwent wide excision and biopsy of the lesion, performed by a surgical oncologist, followed by defect reconstruction by a plastic surgeon using a cheek advancement flap to cover the nasolabial defect. The defect from the wide excision measured 4 cm x 3 cm with an exposed muscle base in the

lateral nasal region of the right nasolabial area with intact oral commissure. The flap was designed, infiltration of lidocaine and epinephrine solution done, and incisions were made extending from lateral nasal, subciliary, and preauricular regions on the right side of face.

Fig 2. Preoperative assessment. Oncologic surgeon performed wide excision of the lesion, resulting in a 4 cm x 3 cm defect on the right nasolabial region with exposure of the muscle.

Fig 3. Immediate postoperative assessment. The cheek advancement flap successfully covered the entire defect, flap was viable and postoperative bleeding controlled.

The flap was dissected above the SMAS (Superficial Musculoaponeurotic System). The wound was then irrigated with 0.9% NaCl and antibiotic solution. A 10Fr drain was secured to prevent hematoma collection. The flap was inset towards the defect. Anchoring sutures were placed to the periosteum of the zygomatic area with 4/0 multifilament absorbable sutures, subcutaneous sutures with 4/0 multifilament absorbable sutures, and skin sutures with 5/0 monofilament non-absorbable sutures. The wound was dressed with gentamicin ointment, non-adherent paraffin dressing, and sterile gauze. Histomorphological evaluation of the anatomical pathology specimen revealed findings consistent with basal cell carcinoma, nodular and infiltrating type. The patient was placed under observation by the surgical oncologist and scheduled for periodic follow-up evaluation. Postoperatively, the patient was fully conscious and hemodynamically stable. Postoperative management included antibiotic therapy with cefixime 200 mg twice daily, intravenous dexamethasone 5 mg twice daily, and intravenous tranexamic acid 500 mg twice daily, along with antiseptic mouth rinses every 4 hours. Patient was also advised on a non-chewing, high protein diet.

During hospitalization, wound care was performed on postoperative day 2 and 6. The flap remained viable, with

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appropriate skin color, no tension, minimal edema and minimal drain output of less than 20 cc in 24 hours post op. Drain was removed on day two post operative. Cranial nerve VII function was assessed, showing bilateral eyebrow elevation and symmetric eye closure, with subtle asymmetry of the right side on smiling/with a mild delay on the right side during smiling. The patient was discharged on postoperative day 6 and scheduled for follow-up in the plastic surgery outpatient clinic five days later for suture removal.

Fig 4. Postoperative follow up. Viable cheek flap with no sign of necrosis, dehiscence, or infection, satisfactory scar maturation and good color match.

At the first outpatient follow-up, day 6 post op, the flap remained viable, with no tension, edema, or signs of necrosis, and good color match with the adjacent skin. Subtle asymmetry on smiling was still observed and was to be reassessed at later follow-up. Sutures were removed, and the wound was managed by secondary intention with topical gentamicin ointment. At the second (day 11 post op) and third follow-ups (week 3 post op), the flap continued to be viable, with satisfactory scar maturation, no slough or necrosis, and good color match, although residual right-sided smile asymmetry persisted. The patient was given mecobalamin 500 mcg daily, and was counseled on photoprotection (sunscreen use and avoidance of direct sunlight), facial muscle rehabilitation was initiated, including exaggerated smiling, lip pursing, and cheek inflation exercises. Topical silicone gel application twice daily was planned once the incision site was no longer erythematous.

III. DISCUSSION

Basal cell carcinoma (BCC) of the face commonly affects sun-exposed regions and may behave locally aggressively if diagnosis or treatment is delayed; elderly patients with prolonged outdoor exposure constitute a high-risk group. Our patient's occupational sun exposure and clinical presentation are consistent with contemporary epidemiologic and clinical descriptions of facial BCC in the reconstructive literature. Immediate attention to oncologic resection with clear margins remains central to management to avoid progressive local tissue loss and functional compromise.^{VII}

The decision for wide local excision followed by immediate reconstruction in this case aligns with recent

outcome data indicating that immediate local flap reconstruction after standard excision of nasal and perinasal BCCs can be undertaken safely, with comparable re-excision and recurrence rates to staged approaches when margins are carefully evaluated. A large retrospective series found no increased risk of re-excision or recurrence following immediate flap reconstruction for nasal BCCs and supports immediate reconstruction as a reasonable option in many clinical settings.^{VIII}

In the present case, a cheek advancement flap was selected to reconstruct a 4 × 3 cm nasolabial and lateral nasal defect. This choice is supported by the flap's reliable vascular supply, favorable advancement vector, and superior color and texture match relative to distant or free flaps. Multiple contemporary series describe the cheek advancement flap as a dependable option for moderate-sized facial defects, providing predictable coverage with low morbidity and high rates of patient satisfaction.^{IX-XI}

Technical decisions such as a supra-SMAS (above the SMAS) dissection as performed here reflect ongoing debate about superficial versus deep-plane flap elevation. A systematic review and meta-analysis comparing superficial versus deep-plane cervicofacial and cheek flap dissections reported low overall complication rates for both approaches and did not identify an increased rate of permanent facial nerve injury with either technique, suggesting that surgeon familiarity and careful dissection may be more important than plane alone in determining outcomes.^{VI} Anatomical studies of facial glide planes and the superficial musculoaponeurotic system (SMAS) demonstrate that the choice of dissection plane should be individualized according to defect location, flap design, and the degree of tissue mobilization required. Careful preservation of facial retaining ligaments during dissection helps maintain vascular integrity and allows smooth redraping of the flap, thereby optimizing both flap perfusion and aesthetic contour.^{XII}

Intra- and postoperative outcomes in this patient—complete flap viability, minimal drain output, no wound necrosis, and only transient smile asymmetry—mirror reported complication profiles for cervicofacial/cheek flaps, where major complications (partial necrosis, dehiscence) are relatively uncommon and total flap loss is rare. The mild right-sided smile asymmetry observed during early follow-up is consistent with findings reported in recent reconstructive series and is most commonly attributed to postoperative edema, traction, or transient neuropraxia rather than permanent facial nerve injury. Contemporary facial nerve literature emphasizes the importance of distinguishing temporary dysfunction from irreversible injury, as the majority of postoperative facial weakness following locoregional flap reconstruction improves with conservative management. Early observation combined with neuromuscular retraining and adjunctive pharmacologic support has been shown to facilitate recovery, improve

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coordination, and reduce the risk of synkinesis. Surgical facial reanimation procedures—including nerve grafting, nerve transfers, or dynamic muscle transfer—are generally reserved for patients with persistent deficits beyond the expected recovery period, underscoring the role of structured follow-up and staged decision-making in optimizing long-term functional and aesthetic outcomes.^{XII-XV}

Optimizing long-term aesthetic and functional outcomes extends beyond flap survival: patient comorbidity, tumor size and subtype, and reconstructive method significantly influence cosmetic results and satisfaction. Predictive models and cohort analyses emphasize the importance of individualized planning, perioperative counseling (including photoprotection), and structured postoperative rehabilitation—measures we implemented in this patient (mecobalamin, facial muscle exercises, topical scar care) to support neuromuscular recovery and scar maturation. These multimodal strategies correlate with improved patient-reported outcomes in recent cohorts of facial BCC reconstruction.^{XVI}

Taken together, the present case demonstrates that for selected moderate-sized nasolabial defects after oncologic excision, a cheek/cervicofacial flap can reliably restore form and function with low morbidity when performed with careful surgical planning, appropriate dissection technique, and attentive postoperative care. This approach is particularly valuable when tissue match, single-stage reconstruction, and avoidance of prolonged microsurgical procedures are priorities.^{IX-XI}

Reconstruction with a cheek advancement flap respected facial aesthetic unit principles and utilized adjacent tissue to achieve favorable color and texture match. At follow-up, healing was satisfactory, and the patient reported satisfaction with the aesthetic appearance of the scar.

CONCLUSIONS

Cheek advancement flap reconstruction following wide excision of a nodular-infiltrating basal cell carcinoma in the nasolabial region provided reliable soft-tissue coverage, preserved nasal and oral commissure function, and achieved satisfactory aesthetic integration in this elderly patient with significant sun-exposure risk. Immediate reconstruction with a locoregional flap, when combined with precise oncologic resection, careful dissection respecting SMAS/glide-plane anatomy, and structured postoperative rehabilitation, offers a reliable solution for moderate-sized facial defects with low complication rates. Transient postoperative facial asymmetry highlights the necessity of continued observation and systematic evaluation of facial nerve function. Incorporating facial nerve monitoring, early rehabilitation, and timely consideration of facial reanimation strategies when indicated is essential for achieving optimal long-term functional and aesthetic outcomes following facial oncologic reconstruction.

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